

Exploring Urban Plastic Waste Recovery: A Spatial Analysis of Junk Shops in Manila City, Philippines

Aerol Cedrick Z. Treyes^{1,*}, Maria Antonia N. Tanchuling^{1,2},
Kayla C. Macadangdang¹

¹ AMH Philippines, Inc., Ang Bahay ng Alumni Building, Barangay U.P. Campus, Diliman, Quezon City, Philippines 1101

² College of Engineering, University of the Philippines, Diliman, Quezon City, Philippines 1101

*Corresponding author: aeroltreyes@gmail.com

Abstract. Plastic waste recovery in cities depends not only on collection, but also on whether recyclable materials can reach accessible recovery nodes with sufficient capacity. This study assessed the spatial distribution, accessibility, capacity, and allocation potential of city-level junk shops trading recyclable plastics in Manila City. Local government records, site verification, and field interviews identified 73 registered junk shops, of which 34 city-level plastic-trading junk shops were analyzed using GIS-based clustering, service coverage, isochrone analysis, capacity assessment, and risk-weighted allocation modeling. Results identified 10 recovery clusters, with about 53% of the city's population lacked direct access within the defined baseline service areas. These clusters had an estimated recyclable plastic recovery potential of 75,785 kg/day and current recovery of 17,937 kg/day, equivalent to 24% utilization within the service area. Under a full-operation scenario, capacity coverage increased to 47%, but optimized allocation still showed remaining service deficits. Priority areas were concentrated where unmet recovery demand, high recyclable plastic generation, and proximity to waterways or coastline overlapped. The study provides a planning-level framework for strengthening access, logistics, feeder recovery points, and junk shop support in urban plastic recovery systems.

Keywords: Geographic Information System (GIS); Junk Shops; Manila City; Plastic Waste; Urban Waste Recovery

1. Introduction

Plastic waste recovery remains a major challenge in the Philippines because a large share of plastics does not enter effective recovery pathways after use. In 2019, the country was reported to consume about 2.15 million metric tons of plastics, where only 9% was recycled, 5% was collected for export, 2% was recovered as refuse-derived fuel, while around 35% leaked into the open environment [1]. These figures show that addressing plastic pollution depends not only on material recyclability and recycling technology, but also on whether recyclable plastics are segregated, collected, traded, transported, and absorbed by facilities or market actors that can consolidate and process them. This makes the movement of plastics after generation an important part of recovery planning, especially in cities where recyclable materials pass through both formal and informal actors. To strengthen this link in the recovery chain, junk shops serve as important local recovery nodes that connect waste generators, informal collectors, consolidators, and end-of-chain processors [1–3].

Junk shops, either registered or unregistered, are widely present in the Philippine waste recovery system, but their contribution depends on their location, accepted materials, operating capacity, market linkages, and accessibility. In practice, they receive recyclable materials from several points in the waste stream, including waste generators, drop-off points, material recovery facilities (MRFs), waste collection vehicles before final disposal, and disposal sites where recoverable materials may still be extracted [3]. The national inventory of junk shops in 2023 documents at least 1,800 registered junk shops across the country, which are mostly concentrated in highly urbanized areas, particularly in Metro Manila or the National Capital Region (NCR) [3, 4]. This concentration is important because urban areas generate large amounts of recyclables, but recovery activities are also constrained by limited space, market demand, traffic conditions, and fragmented waste flows. These conditions are evident in Manila City, a dense and highly urbanized coastal city within NCR connected by multiple waterways draining to Manila Bay. Previous baseline assessment showed that the city has high municipal solid waste generation, limited recovery performance, and significant plastic leakage to the environment [5]. In this setting, improving plastic recovery depends not only on whether waste is collected by the formal system, but also on whether recyclable plastics can move through accessible and functional recovery pathways.

Several solid waste and plastic leakage assessments in the country commonly quantify waste generation, waste composition, collection coverage, recycling performance, and leakage pathways [1, 3, 5–9]. These approaches are useful for understanding the amount, composition, and waste flows in a study area, but they do not fully explain whether local recovery networks are spatially positioned and operationally capable of absorbing recyclable materials. In parallel, international waste studies using geographic information system (GIS) have demonstrated the value of service area analysis, accessibility assessment, network analysis, and location-allocation models in improving waste facility planning, collection point siting, route optimization, and population coverage [10–13]. Limited attention, however, has been given to the spatial functionality of junk shops in the country as private recovery nodes that operate between formal solid waste systems and informal collection networks. This gap is important because the effectiveness of junk shops depends on their location, accessibility, reported capacity, spatial relationship with recyclable plastic demand, and proximity to areas where leakage consequences may be higher.

This study addresses this gap by assessing the spatial distribution and recovery potential of city-level junk shops trading recyclable plastics in Manila City. Specifically, it evaluates service coverage, accessibility, reported recovery capacity, and capacity-constrained allocation of recyclable plastic demand to identify areas where recovery gaps remain. The study also considers proximity to waterways and coastline to highlight priority areas where unmet recovery potential may have greater leakage implications. By combining local government records, field interviews, GIS-based accessibility analysis, and planning-level allocation modeling, the study aims to provide spatial evidence that can support more targeted plastic recovery planning. The findings are intended to help local governments, planners, and recovery actors identify where access, logistics, feeder recovery points, and junk shop support may be strengthened to improve urban plastic waste recovery.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study area

The study was conducted in the City of Manila, the capital city of the Philippines, located on the eastern coast of Manila Bay and at the mouth of the Pasig River (Figure 1). The city covers about 43 km² and had a population of about 1.90 million in 2024 [6, 14]. It is composed of 896 barangays (villages) grouped into 16 administrative districts and six congressional districts [5]. Its urban form, high population density, limited land area, and concentration of residential, commercial, institutional, and industrial activities place a strong pressure on the local solid waste management system. The city is also

traversed by the Pasig River and several creeks, esteros, and drainage channels that eventually discharge westward to Manila Bay, making unmanaged or unrecovered plastics a direct concern for urban waterway and coastal pollution [5, 6].

Figure 1. Study area and city-level junk shops in Manila City.

Manila provides a suitable case for assessing junk shop accessibility and recovery networks because high waste generation occurs within a dense and spatially constrained urban setting. Based on the 2023 Waste Analysis and Characterization Study (WACS), the per capita waste generation rate of the city is at 0.938 kg/cap/day, equivalent to 1,732 t/day of municipal solid waste, with recyclables accounting for 24.37% of generated waste [15]. Recyclable plastics accounted for about 8.2% of municipal solid waste, or about 142 t/day, following the National Solid Waste Management Commission (NSWMC) classification used in WACS. This classification excludes residual plastic materials with potential for recycling but with limited recovery markets in the country, such as sachets and similar flexible packaging [15, 16]. Baseline assessment in 2021 also estimated a municipal solid waste collection rate of 86% and recovery rate of 13% of generated municipal solid waste, indicating that a large amount of generated waste still proceeds to disposal or remains at risk of leakage despite formal collection services [5]. These conditions provide a practical basis for examining whether the location, accessibility, and reported capacity of junk shops can support recyclable plastic recovery in a dense urban environment.

2.2. Analytical framework

The study used a GIS-based planning framework to assess whether city-level junk shops trading recyclable plastics are spatially accessible and operationally capable of supporting plastic recovery in Manila City (Figure 2). The analysis was based on local government records [17], site verification, and field interviews (see supplementary material) conducted from January to February 2024. From the local inventory, 73 registered junk shops were identified, of which 34 were classified as city-level junk shops trading plastics and were included in the analysis. In this study, city-level junk shops refer to larger recovery nodes that receive recyclable materials from waste generators, informal collectors, smaller junk shops, barangay MRFs, collection vehicles prior to disposal, and that can transact directly with regional

consolidators or end-of-chain processors. This focus was adopted to represent the higher-level recovery network while reducing possible double counting, since recyclable plastics handled by smaller junk shops or individual collectors are commonly consolidated through these larger, city-level junk shops before being sold onward [1].

Figure 2. GIS-based analytical framework for city-level junk shop recovery networks.

The framework proceeded from junk shop mapping and classification to clustering, service coverage, capacity and utilization assessment, accessibility modeling, risk-weighted allocation, and priority mapping. These components used the selected city-level junk shops as recovery nodes and recyclable plastic generation as the main demand basis, allowing the analysis to move from mapping existing recovery conditions to identifying spatial, capacity, and priority gaps.

2.3. Junk shop clustering, coverage, capacity, and utilization

The spatial distribution of the city-level junk shops trading recyclable plastics was analyzed in QGIS to identify local recovery clusters and estimate their potential service areas. Junk shop locations were mapped as point features and grouped using density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise (DBSCAN), with a 1,000-m search distance and a minimum cluster size of one point. This approach allowed nearby junk shops to be treated as recovery clusters while retaining isolated facilities as single-node clusters. A common 500-m buffer was first applied around each city-level junk shop to represent an ideal local access distance for small-volume recyclable movement. For cluster-level assessment, the individual junk shop buffers within each cluster were represented by an equivalent cluster service area centered on the cluster centroid, using the farthest extent of the member junk shop buffers but not exceeding the 1,000-m clustering distance. This provided a consistent planning-level basis for comparing service coverage across clusters without treating the buffer as an exact operational catchment. Citywide service coverage was calculated as the share of the total population or estimated recyclable plastic demand located within the combined cluster service areas (Equation 1). Population distribution was based on 2020 WorldPop gridded population data (1,680,343) at approximately 100-m resolution, adjusted to the 2024 population of Manila City (1,902,590) [14, 18]. This indicator was used to show which parts of the city are spatially near existing recovery clusters and which areas remain outside the immediate access zone.

$$SC = \frac{P_{CSA}}{P_T} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where SC is the citywide service coverage (%), P_{CSA} is the population within all cluster service areas, and P_T is the total population in the city. Since the recyclable plastic demand in this study was estimated using a constant per capita generation factor, the same service coverage proportion can be used to represent the share of estimated recyclable plastic demand covered within the cluster service areas.

Capacity and utilization were assessed by comparing estimated recyclable plastic demand with the reported plastic recovery capacity of each junk shop cluster. Cluster capacity was computed as the sum of the reported daily plastic recovery capacities of the city-level junk shops within each cluster. The reported capacity was based on field interviews with junk shop operators and represents the approximate amount of recyclable plastics that the facility or cluster should handle per day under its existing operating conditions. Recovery potential refers to the estimated recyclable plastic generation within the cluster service area (Equation 2). Recovery utilization was defined as the reported amount of recyclable plastics received or recovered by the cluster relative to the estimated recovery potential within its service area (Equation 3). Capacity coverage was defined as the reported maximum plastic recovery capacity of the cluster relative to the same estimated recovery potential (Equation 4). These indicators were used together because spatial proximity alone does not show whether nearby recovery clusters are already receiving recyclable plastics or have enough reported capacity to absorb additional local recovery demand (Table 1).

$$RP_i = P_i \times G_{RP} \quad (2)$$

where RP_i is the estimated recyclable plastic recovery potential within the service area of cluster i (kg/day), P_i is the population within the service area of cluster i , and G_{RP} is the recyclable plastic generation factor (kg/cap/day). In this study, G_{RP} is equivalent to the product of the per capita waste generation rate of 0.938 kg/cap/day and recyclable plastic composition of 8.28% of the total municipal solid waste [15].

$$RU_i = \frac{R_i}{RP_i} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where RU_i is the recovery utilization of cluster i (%) and R_i is the reported amount of recyclable plastics received or recovered by the cluster (kg/day).

$$CC_i = \frac{C_i}{RP_i} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where CC_i is the capacity coverage of cluster i (%) and C_i is the reported maximum plastic recovery capacity of the cluster (kg/day).

Table 1. Classification of recovery utilization and capacity coverage.

Indicator	Basis	Classification	Interpretation
Recovery utilization	$RU_i < 50\%$	Low	The cluster receives less than half of the estimated recyclable plastic recovery potential within its service area.
	$50\% \leq RU_i \leq 100\%$	Adequate	The cluster receives an amount broadly comparable to the estimated recovery potential within its service area.
	$RU_i > 100\%$	High	The cluster receives more than the estimated recovery potential within its service area, suggesting possible inflow from outside the defined service area.

Indicator	Basis	Classification	Interpretation
Capacity coverage	$CC_i < 50\%$	Deficit	The reported maximum capacity can accommodate less than half of the estimated recovery potential within its service area.
	$50\% \leq CC_i \leq 100\%$	Adequate	The reported maximum capacity can accommodate a substantial share of the estimated recovery potential within its service area.
	$CC_i > 100\%$	Surplus	The reported maximum capacity exceeds the estimated recovery potential within its service area.

Note: Recovery utilization reflects reported current recovery activity under existing operating conditions, while capacity coverage reflects reported estimated maximum handling capacity.

2.4. Accessibility modeling

Accessibility to city-level junk shops trading plastics was assessed using QGIS Network Analysis Toolbox 3 (QNEAT3) plugin in QGIS and OpenStreetMap (OSM) road network data in the city extracted in February 2025. Isochrone analysis was conducted for walking (5-minute interval) and driving (2.5-minute interval) scenarios to represent different ways recyclable plastics may reach junk shops. The walking scenario was used to approximate small-volume movement by households, informal collectors, and nearby generators, while driving scenarios represented vehicle-based movement by junk shops, collection vehicles, or other actors handling larger recyclable volumes. Walking speed was assigned based on reference pedestrian travel speeds with 10% assumed reduction to account for carrying recyclables, while vehicle speeds were assigned according to road classification and applicable speed limit guidance for trucks and similar vehicles (Table 2).

Table 2. Considered speed limits according to road/activity classification.

Road/Activity Classification	Speed	Reference
Expressways and Highways	60 kph ^a	[19]
Through Streets and City/Municipal Streets (trunk, primary, secondary, tertiary, links)	30 kph	[20, 21]
Crowded Streets (residential, service, street, unclassified)	20 kph	[20, 21]
Other Roads and Walking	4 kph ^b	[22]

^a Lowest maximum speed limit for highways/expressways (curved sections).

^b Estimated average walking speed (~4.5 kph) with applied 10% reduction for carrying heavy loads (recyclables).

Driving accessibility was further assessed under adjusted traffic conditions to reflect the effect of congestion in the city. Baseline driving isochrones were first generated using road-class speed assumptions. Additional driving scenarios were then generated applying the TomTom Traffic Index congestion levels for Manila in 2024, including average congestion (42%), morning rush hour congestion (55%), and evening rush hour congestion (88%) [23, 24]. These congestion values were applied uniformly to the road network as travel-time multipliers; equivalently, the baseline road speeds were divided by $1 + c$, where c is the congestion level expressed as a decimal. The accessibility modeling was used only as a planning-level estimate of potential travel reach and did not represent real-time routing, route choice, or daily operational decisions of junk shop operators and collectors.

2.5. Risk-weighted capacity allocation and priority mapping

A risk-weighted capacity allocation model was developed to assess how estimated recyclable plastic demand could be assigned to existing junk shop clusters under travel-time and capacity constraints. In QGIS, the city was divided into 500-m grid cells to simplify demand allocation and reduce the effect of very small spatial units. The WorldPop population raster (~100 m) was resampled and aggregated to the 500-m grid using QGIS raster processing tools to estimate the population within each demand cell. The recyclable plastic demand of each cell was estimated from its population and the recyclable plastic generation factor used in this study. The supply nodes were represented by the junk shop clusters, with each cluster assigned its reports maximum plastic recovery capacity based on field interviews. To reflect possible leakage consequences, each demand cell was also assigned a proximity-based risk weight using the distance from its centroid to the nearest waterway or coastline (Manila Bay). The distance values were min-max normalized so that cells closer to waterways or coasts received higher risk values (Equation 5). This risk weight was used only as a planning indicator for prioritization and not as a direct estimate of actual plastic leakage.

$$\text{Risk}_j = \frac{d_{\max} - d_j}{d_{\max} - d_{\min}} \quad (5)$$

where Risk_j is the normalized proximity-based risk weight of demand cell j , d_j is the distance from cell j to the nearest waterway or coastline, and d_{\min} and d_{\max} are the minimum and maximum distances among all demand cells considered.

An origin-destination (OD) travel-time matrix was then generated using QNEAT3 plugin based on the road network and average congestion-adjusted driving condition. The matrix linked each demand cell centroid to each junk shop cluster centroid and provided the travel-time cost used in the allocation model. The allocation problem was solved in OpenSolver using COIN-OR Branch-and-Cut (CBC) model commonly used for linear programming [25], with decision variables representing the amount of recyclable plastic demand assigned from each cell to each cluster. The model minimized the total allocation cost by considering travel time for served demand and a penalty for unmet demand (Equation 6), while ensuring that each cell's demand was either assigned to a cluster or left unmet, cluster capacities were not exceeded, and allocation values remained non-negative (Equation 7). For demand cells within 500 m of a cluster node, an additional local-service constraint was applied to limit the share of demand that could remain unmet at 50%. This reflects the assumption that areas nearest to existing recovery nodes should be served first where capacity allows.

$$p_j = P_{\text{base}}(1 + \text{Risk}_j) \quad (6)$$

where p_j is the unmet-demand penalty for cell j , and P_{base} is the baseline penalty derived from the maximum nearest-cluster travel time in the OD matrix. This ensured that leaving demand unmet was penalized more strongly for cells closer to waterways or the coastline.

$$\text{Minimize } Z = \sum_{j \in J} \sum_{i \in I} (t_{i,j} \cdot x_{i,j}) + \sum_{j \in J} p_j \cdot u_j \quad (7)$$

subject to:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i \in I} x_{i,j} + u_j &= D_j \quad \forall j \in J \\ \sum_{j \in J} x_{i,j} &\leq C_i \quad \forall i \in I \\ u_j &\leq [(1 - N_j) + \varepsilon N_j] D_j \quad \forall j \in J \\ x_{i,j} &\geq 0 \quad \forall i \in I, \forall j \in J \\ u_j &\geq 0 \quad \forall j \in J \end{aligned}$$

where Z is the total allocation cost, I is the set of junk shop clusters, J is the set of demand cells, t_{ij} is the travel time from demand cell j to cluster i , x_{ij} is the allocated recyclable plastic demand from cell j to cluster i , u_j is the unmet demand in cell j , D_j is the recyclable plastic demand for cell j , C_i is the reported maximum plastic recovery capacity of cluster i , N_j is equal to 1 when cell j is within 500 m of a cluster node and 0 otherwise, and ϵ is the maximum allowable unmet share for cells within 500 m of a cluster node (assumed at 50%).

The optimized allocation outputs were mapped to identify assigned service areas, remaining unmet demand, and priority intervention areas. Priority areas were interpreted as locations where high recyclable plastic demand, high proximity-based leakage risk, and unmet recovery demand overlapped (Table 3). For local planning interpretation in this study, the grid-based outputs were also summarized by barangay to help identify where additional collection linkages, feeder recovery points, or capacity support may be most needed.

Table 3. Criteria for identifying priority intervention areas.

Priority Class	Criteria	Planning Interpretation
High generation, high risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Top 20 cells with highest recyclable plastic generation (demand) • Top 20 cells with highest proximity-based risk • Unmet service share $\geq 25\%$ 	Areas where high demand, high waterway/coastal proximity, and remaining service gaps overlap
Low generation, high risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Top 20 cells with highest proximity-based risk • Unmet service share $> 0\%$ 	Areas near waterways or coastline where even smaller unmet demand may still have leakage relevance
High generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Top 20 cells with highest recyclable plastic generation (demand) • Unmet service share $\geq 50\%$ 	Areas where large recyclable plastic demand remains insufficiently served despite lower relative proximity to waterways/coastline

2.6. Assumptions and limitations

The analysis was based on several assumptions to support a planning-level assessment of junk shop accessibility and recyclable plastic recovery in Manila City. The study focused only on recyclable plastics based on NSWMC classification used in the 2023 WACS data, and excluded residual plastic materials with limited recovery markets. Recyclable plastic demand was estimated using population-based spatial allocation and a constant recyclable plastic generation factor, assuming proportionality with population distribution. The study also focused on Manila City and did not explicitly model recovery flows from adjacent cities, although junk shop trading and downstream recycling markets may extend beyond the city boundary. The analysis covered city-level junk shops accepting plastics as identified from local government records, site verification, and field interviews. Smaller, informal, or unregistered junk shops were excluded to avoid possible double counting of processed recyclables. Partner-led plastic recovery initiatives using designated collection points or events were also outside the scope of the study, particularly those targeting residual plastics not commonly accepted by junk shops.

The results should be interpreted within these data and modeling boundaries. Reported capacity values were based on interviews with junk shop operators and may vary by season, operating conditions, storage availability, material quality, market demand, and buyer arrangements. Travel times from isochrone and OD analyses were scenario-based and used road network, speed, and congestion

assumptions. These do not represent real-time traffic variability, loading and unloading delays, road obstructions, or daily route choices. The allocation model was designed as a planning-level optimization under stated constraints, and did not model prices, collector behavior, negotiations, operating schedules, or daily decisions of operators and collectors. These limitations define the use of the results as spatial planning evidence for identifying service gaps, capacity constraints, and priority areas.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Spatial distribution and baseline service gaps

The spatial analysis identified 10 recovery clusters among the 34 city-level junk shops trading recyclable plastics in Manila City (Figure 3). These clusters were not evenly distributed across the city, with several recovery nodes concentrated in selected areas while other high-density communities remained outside the defined baseline service areas. Based on the service coverage assessment, about 53% of the city’s population lacked direct access to city-level junk shops that accommodate recyclable plastics within the defined service coverage area. This indicates that the presence of junk shops within the city does not necessarily translate to even spatial access, particularly where recovery nodes are distant from dense residential areas or areas with high recyclable plastic generation.

Figure 3. Spatial distribution, clustering, and baseline service coverage of city-level junk shops in Manila City. (a) spatial distribution and clustering of city-level junk shops trading recyclable plastics; (b) baseline service coverage of junk shop clusters relative to 2024 population distribution.

The most pronounced baseline service gap was observed in District I (Tondo), where high population density and high estimated waste generation overlap with limited coverage from the selected city-level recovery clusters. This does not imply the absence of smaller junk shops or informal recovery activities in the district. Rather, it indicates that the identified city-level nodes may not provide sufficient direct spatial coverage relative to the scale of local recyclable plastic demand. This pattern suggests the need to improve local recovery linkages in underserved areas, especially for households, informal collectors, and small-volume generators that depend on nearby buyers, feeder points, or accessible recovery channels.

3.2. Capacity and utilization of city-level junk shop clusters

The 10 junk shop clusters had an estimated recyclable plastic recovery potential of about 75,785 kg/day within their service areas (Table 4). Based on field interviews, the clusters were receiving about 17,937 kg/day of recyclable plastics at the time of the study, equivalent to an overall recovery utilization of 24%. Most clusters had low utilization, with only one cluster reaching the adequate range. This pattern indicates that many clusters were not receiving recyclable plastics at a level comparable to the estimated recovery potential within their surrounding service areas.

Table 4. Recovery potential, utilization, and capacity coverage by junk shop cluster.

Cluster	Reported Current Cluster Capacity (kg/day)	Estimated Recovery Potential (kg/day)	Recovery Utilization (%)	Capacity Coverage (%)
1	4,630	17,963	26% (low)	52% (adequate)
2	1,143	1,681	68% (adequate)	136% (surplus)
3	3,952	10,993	36% (low)	72% (adequate)
4	2,700	10,937	25% (low)	49% (deficit)
5	1,894	4,170	45% (low)	91% (adequate)
6	528	6,026	9% (low)	18% (deficit)
7	1,279	13,547	9% (low)	19% (deficit)
8	229	1,352	17% (low)	34% (deficit)
9	1,055	6,718	16% (low)	31% (deficit)
10	528	2,397	22% (low)	44% (deficit)
Total	17,937	75,785	24% (low)	47% (deficit)

Capacity coverage was assessed using the estimated maximum handling capacity of the junk shops. Since operators reported that current activity was generally about half of the maximum amount they could accommodate, the maximum handling capacity was estimated at twice the reported current recovery level. Under this full-operation scenario, the overall maximum capacity coverage increased to about 47%. This value, however, remains below the estimated recyclable plastic recovery potential within the service areas, indicating that capacity remains a constraint even when existing clusters are assumed to operate at maximum reported capacity. This finding shows that recovery gaps are not only caused by spatial access, but also by the limited ability of existing city-level junk shops to absorb recyclable plastics generated nearby.

3.3. Accessibility and logistics conditions

Accessibility results show different conditions for small-volume movement and vehicle-based logistics (Figure 4). Based on the walking scenario, about 40% of the city's population could reach a city-level junk shop trading recyclable plastics within 10 minutes. This indicates that near-range access remains limited for household, informal collectors, itinerant buyers, and small-volume generators that may depend on walking or short manual movement to bring recyclables to nearby recovery points.

Figure 4. Walking and driving accessibility to city-level junk shops in Manila City. (a) walking accessibility; (b) driving accessibility based on road design speed; (c) driving accessibility under average congestion; (d) driving accessibility under morning rush-hour congestion; (e) driving accessibility under afternoon rush-hour congestion.

Vehicle-based access was substantially higher, but it was affected by congestion. Under design-speed conditions, about 97% of the population was within 5 minutes of driving from a city-level junk shop. Since recyclable plastic demand was estimated using a constant per capita generation factor, this also suggests that about 97% of estimated recyclable plastic demand was located within the same 5-minute driving catchment. When average congestion was applied, this decreased to about 89%, showing that traffic conditions can reduce practical logistics access even when recovery nodes are physically near. Accessibility, however, should be interpreted as an enabling condition rather than a direct measure of recovery performance, since previous studies indicate that collection and recovery outcomes are also shaped by behavioral, operational, institutional, and system-level factors [7, 10, 26]. These results suggest that driving access can support broader hauling and collection linkages, but high vehicle accessibility does not automatically translate to higher recovery if capacity and operational coordination remain limited.

3.4. Optimized allocation and remaining service deficits

The optimized allocation model assigned recyclable plastic demand to the 10 junk shop clusters based on travel time, reported maximum cluster capacity, and the risk-weighted unmet-demand penalty (Figure 5). The resulting cluster service map provides a planning-level estimate of which areas can be served by the existing network under constrained conditions, consistent with the use of GIS-based allocation models for waste management system planning [11–13]. Even under this optimized assignment, the current network could not absorb all recyclable plastic demand generated within the assigned service areas. This shows that allocation was limited not only by the spatial reach of the clusters, but also by their reported handling capacities, leaving some demand unmet even in areas assigned to nearby recovery nodes.

Figure 5. Optimized allocation of recyclable plastic demand to city-level junk shop clusters in Manila City. (a) 500-m grid-based recyclable plastic generation; (b) grid-based optimized cluster service areas; (c) barangay-based optimized cluster service areas.

The cluster-level summary further confirms that all assigned service areas remained capacity-constrained (Table 5; see supplementary material). The maximum capacity-to-demand ratios ranged from 8% to 89%, indicating that no cluster could fully absorb the recyclable plastics generated within its optimized service area. Some clusters showed relatively stronger capacity-to-demand relationships, while others remained highly deficient. This pattern suggests that the remaining recovery gaps are structural, rather than purely spatial. Under the current network, improving recovery would likely require additional feeder nodes, stronger collection linkages, or targeted capacity support rather than relying only on the existing city-level junk shop clusters.

Table 5. Optimized cluster service areas for recyclable plastic recovery in Manila City.

Cluster	Maximum Cluster Capacity (kg/day)	No. of Optimized Barangays	Recyclable Plastic Generation (Demand) in Opt. Barangays (kg/day)	Capacity / Demand (%)
1	9,260	75	10,366	89%
2	2,286	33	3,641	63%
3	7,904	87	9,837	80%
4	5,400	30	9,614	56%
5	3,788	12	6,790	56%
6	1,055	5	2,069	51%
7	2,558	40	4,402	58%
8	457	1	5,419	8%
9	2,110	28	3,768	56%
10	1,055	11	1,892	56%
Total	35,873	322	57,798	62%

3.5. Priority intervention areas for urban plastic recovery

Priority intervention areas were identified where unmet recovery demand overlapped with high recyclable plastic generation and higher proximity-based leakage risk (Figure 6). These areas should be interpreted as planning-screening outputs rather than fixed project sites, since they indicate where recovery access may provide the greatest benefit under the modeled conditions. The results show that priority areas were concentrated near waterways, the coastline, and dense urban districts where remaining service gaps were still present. This pattern is consistent with assessments in the city and in the region that identify waterways and coastal drainage pathways as important routes for plastic leakage when collection, recovery, and containment systems are limited [3, 5, 6].

Figure 6. Priority intervention areas for recyclable plastic recovery in Manila City. (a) grid-based priority intervention map; (b) barangay-based priority intervention map.

At the district level, District VI had the highest indicative recovery support need, with 119 barangays identified for prioritization and an estimated 25,487 kg/day of recyclable plastic generation within these priority areas (Table 6; see supplementary material). This does not necessarily mean that all priority barangays require new junk shops. The estimated number of additional junk shops or support recovery nodes, based on an assumed capacity of 1,000 kg/day, should be treated only as an indicative scale of support. In practice, these needs may be addressed through a combination of improvement in capacity, operations, logistics, and system support among existing recovery actors.

Table 6. District-level priority intervention areas and indicative recovery support needs in Manila City.

Congressional District	No. of Barangays to Prioritize	Recyclable Plastic Generation (kg/day)	Equivalent Additional Junk Shops ^a
I	75	9,423	10
II	83	11,657	12
III	43	15,542	16
IV	19	3,065	4
V	16	3,579	4
VI	119	25,487	26
Total	355	68,753	72

^a Considering an operational capacity of 1,000 kg/day for recyclable plastics.

3.6. Planning implications for local plastic recovery systems

The findings indicate that local plastic recovery planning should address access, logistics, and service allocation, not only the presence of recycling facilities or downstream markets. Existing policy and planning frameworks already recognized the importance of segregation, materials recovery, private sector participation, and extended producer responsibility (EPR) in improving waste recovery [3, 27–29]. The results, however, show that these mechanisms require spatial support at the local level so that recyclable plastics can move efficiently from waste generators, informal collectors, and smaller recovery actors to city-level junk shops and downstream processors. In urban areas such as Manila City, junk shops should therefore be viewed as part of the practical recovery infrastructure, especially in areas where formal collection exists but recyclable plastics may still bypass recovery pathways due to weak access, limited capacity, fragmented collection linkages, or insufficient market-facing recovery channels [1, 3, 5, 7–9].

The priority areas identified in this study can support more targeted interventions by showing where unmet demand, high waste generation, and leakage-sensitive locations overlap. Instead of treating additional junk shops as the only solution, local planning can consider a mix of feeder recovery points, barangay MRF strengthening, scheduled recyclable collection, mobile buying stations, partner-supported plastic collection schemes, and improved logistics between collectors and city-level junk shops. These measures are consistent with broader recommendations to strengthen local recovery systems, integrate informal and private actors, improve plastic waste data, and support circular economy and EPR implementation [1, 3, 5, 7–9]. For local governments, the value of the analysis is not only in identifying where gaps exist, but also in translating those gaps into specific spatial planning questions, such as where recovery access is weak, where existing capacity is insufficient, where linkages should be improved, and where interventions may reduce the risk that recyclable plastics are disposed of or leaked to the environment.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study assessed the spatial distribution, accessibility, capacity, and allocation potential of city-level junk shops trading recyclable plastics in Manila City. The results show that the existing junk shop network contributes to urban plastic waste recovery but remains constrained by spatial service gaps, limited direct access, and insufficient capacity relative to estimated recyclable plastic generation or demand. Although 10 recovery clusters were identified, a large share of the city's population remained outside the defined baseline service areas, and maximum cluster capacities could not fully absorb recyclable plastics under optimized allocation. Priority areas were concentrated where unmet recovery demand, high recyclable plastic generation, and proximity to waterways or coastline overlapped. These findings indicate that improving plastic recovery in dense urban areas requires attention not only to the presence of junk shops, but also to their accessibility, handling capacity, and connection with local collection and recovery pathways.

Based on these findings, local plastic recovery planning should strengthen the linkages among barangays, informal collectors, smaller recovery actors, private recovery initiatives, city-level junk shops, and downstream consolidators and end-of-chain processors. These efforts should be supported by better data systems together with socio-behavioral change communication (SBCC) strategies that encourage segregation, participation, and safe recovery practices. Future work should validate reported capacities through longer monitoring, document actual day-to-day flows, examine the role of smaller and unregistered junk shops and partner-led collection initiatives as possible feeder or support mechanisms where data are available, account for market prices and collector behavior, test the framework in other dense cities, and expand the analysis to other residual plastic categories.

Data Availability Statement

All secondary datasets used in this study are publicly available, with sources cited in the Methodology section. Geospatial outputs and derived data generated from this study are available upon request from the corresponding author.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgment

This study was developed based on the collected datasets under the Plastic Smart Cities (PSC) initiative of the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) Philippines. This initiative is supported by the Norwegian Broadcasting Corporation (NRK) TV-Aksjonen, Norwegian Agency for Development Cooperation (NORAD), and WWF Norway, in partnership with the City of Manila.

References

1. WWF Philippines, cyclos GmbH, AMH Philippines, Inc. (2020) EPR Scheme Assessment for Plastic Packaging Waste in the Philippines. World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) Philippines, Quezon City
2. Lee J, Han H, Park J-Y, Lee D (2021) Urban Informatics in Sustainable Waste Management: A Spatial Analysis of Korea's Informal Recycling Networks. *Sustainability* 13:3076. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063076>
3. World Bank (2024) Guidance on the Development of a Roadmap for Managing Plastic Waste and Reduction of Non-Recyclable Single-use Plastics in the Philippines. Washington, DC: World Bank
4. NSWMC (2025) Junk Shops and Recycling Facilities (2023)
5. AMH Philippines, Inc. (2022) Solid Waste Management Baseline Assessment and Waste Analysis and Characterization Study in City of Manila. World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) Philippines, Quezon City. <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/2cd6f19755884cbfb1b4069cfc52a98>. Accessed 30 May 2026
6. World Bank (2022) An Assessment of Municipal Solid Waste Plans, Collection, Recycling and Disposal of Metro Manila. Washington, DC
7. Osorio E, Bularan L, Tanchuling M, et al (2023) Comprehensive assessment of solid waste management of a highly urbanized city in Metro Manila, Philippines during the COVID-19 pandemic. *IOP Conf Ser: Earth Environ Sci* 1257:012010. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1257/1/012010>
8. PEMSEA (2025) Baseline Assessment Report on Marine Plastics in the Six ODA Project Sites in the Philippines. Partnerships in Environmental Management for the Seas of East Asia (PEMSEA), Quezon City. <https://www.pemsea.org/index.php/resources/publications/reports/baseline-assessment-report-marine-plastics-six-oda-project-sites>. Accessed 30 May 2026
9. Whiteman, Andrew, Cottom, Josh, Baias-Oros A, et al (2023) The Waste Flow Diagram: Identifying Leakages from Municipal Waste Management Systems - Compendium of Case Studies. Deutsche Gesellschaft für Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH, Eschborn
10. Senoglu K, Messmann L (2026) Measuring spatial access to recovery networks for WEEE: The Bavarian case. *Cleaner Waste Systems* 14:100515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clwas.2026.100515>
11. Karimi N, Ng KTW, Richter A (2022) Integrating Geographic Information System network analysis and nighttime light satellite imagery to optimize landfill regionalization on a regional level. *Environ Sci Pollut Res* 29:81492–81504. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-21462-w>
12. Kwikima MM, Ngole F (2025) GIS-based optimization of solid waste collection points and routes: A case study of Majengo Ward, Sumbawanga Municipality, Tanzania. *Cleaner Waste Systems* 12:100372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clwas.2025.100372>

13. Chalkias C, Lasaridi K A GIS based model for the optimisation of municipal solid waste collection: the case study of Nikea, Athens, Greece
14. PSA (2025) 2024 Census of Population (POPCEN) - Population and PGR by Region, Province/HUC, and City/Municipality [Dataset]. <https://psa.gov.ph/content/2024-census-population-popcen-population-counts-declared-official-president>. Accessed 8 June 2026
15. MMDA (2023) Waste Analysis and Characterization Study (2023). Metropolitan Manila Development Authority (MMDA)
16. NSWMC (2021) Waste Analysis and Characterization Study (WACS): A standardized and mandatory guide for Philippine Local Government Units and Solid Waste Management Practitioners
17. Manila DPS (2024) List of DPS-provided Junk Shops and Partner Orgs in Manila
18. Bondarenko, M., Kerr, D., Sorichetta, A., Tatem, A.J. (2020) Census/projection-disaggregated gridded population datasets, adjusted to match the corresponding UNPD 2020 estimates, for 183 countries in 2020 using Built-Settlement Growth Model (BSGM) outputs [Dataset]. WorldPop, University of Southampton. <https://doi.org/10.5258/SOTON/WP00685>.
19. SMC (2025) NAIAX, portions of Skyway Stage 3 speed limits adjusted to 80 kph. In: San Miguel Corporation (SMC). <https://www.sanmiguel.com.ph/corporate/news/naiax-portions-of-skyway-stage-3-speed-limits-adjusted-to-80-kph>. Accessed 8 Jan 2026
20. Republic of the Philippines (1964) Land Transportation and Traffic Code (RA 4136)
21. Joint DOTr, DPWH, DILG (2018) Guidelines and Standards for the Classification of Roads, Setting of Speed Limits Under Republic Act No. 4136, and Collection of Road Crash Data (Joint MC 2018-001)
22. Alves F, Cruz S, Ribeiro A, et al (2020) Walkability Index for Elderly Health: A Proposal. *Sustainability* 12:7360. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12187360>
23. TomTom (2025) Manila 2024 Traffic Index. <https://www.tomtom.com/traffic-index/manila-traffic/>. Accessed 8 January 2026
24. TomTom (2025) About TomTom Traffic Index. In: TomTom. <https://www.tomtom.com/traffic-index/about/>. Accessed 8 Jan 2026
25. Mason AJ (2012) OpenSolver - An Open Source Add-in to Solve Linear and Integer Programmes in Excel. In: Klatt D, Lüthi H-J, Schmedders K (eds) *Operations Research Proceedings 2011*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp 401–406. http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-29210-1_64
26. Treyes AC, Osorio E, Tanchuling MA, et al (2023) Socio-behavioral assessment of household solid waste management: The case of Barangay Calicanto, Philippines. *IOP Conf Ser: Earth Environ Sci* 1257:012008. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1257/1/012008>
27. Republic of the Philippines (2001) Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 (RA 9003)
28. Republic of the Philippines (2022) Extended Producer Responsibility Act of 2022 (RA 11898)
29. NSWMC (2004) National Solid Waste Management Framework. National Solid Waste Management Commission (NSWMC), Quezon City

List of Figures

Figure 1. Study area and city-level junk shops in Manila City. 3

Figure 2. GIS-based analytical framework for city-level junk shop recovery networks. 4

Figure 3. Spatial distribution, clustering, and baseline service coverage of city-level junk shops in Manila City. (a) spatial distribution and clustering of city-level junk shops trading recyclable plastics; (b) baseline service coverage of junk shop clusters relative to 2024 population distribution. 9

Figure 4. Walking and driving accessibility to city-level junk shops in Manila City. (a) walking accessibility; (b) driving accessibility based on road design speed; (c) driving accessibility under average congestion; (d) driving accessibility under morning rush-hour congestion; (e) driving accessibility under afternoon rush-hour congestion. 11

Figure 5. Optimized allocation of recyclable plastic demand to city-level junk shop clusters in Manila City. (a) 500-m grid-based recyclable plastic generation; (b) grid-based optimized cluster service areas; (c) barangay-based optimized cluster service areas. 12

Figure 6. Priority intervention areas for recyclable plastic recovery in Manila City. (a) grid-based priority intervention map; (b) barangay-based priority intervention map. 13

List of Tables

Table 1. Classification of recovery utilization and capacity coverage. 5

Table 2. Considered speed limits according to road/activity classification. 6

Table 3. Criteria for identifying priority intervention areas. 8

Table 4. Recovery potential, utilization, and capacity coverage by junk shop cluster. 10

Table 5. Optimized cluster service areas for recyclable plastic recovery in Manila City. 12

Table 6. District-level priority intervention areas and indicative recovery support needs in Manila City. 13